

*Article***On The Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Fractional Calculus**Necati Olgun¹, and Hatice Kahraman^{2,*}¹ Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep University, Turkey 1; olgun@gantep.edu.tr² Department of Mathematics, Gaziantep University, Turkey 1; kahramannhatiice@gmail.com* Correspondence: kahramannhatiice@gmail.com

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Abstract: Depending on the geometric isometry (AH-Isometry) the foundation of the symbolic 2-plithogenic calculus was established, where new definitions of symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional integration and symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional differentiation were introduced, along with some illustrative examples. Following that, definitions for the symbolic 2-plithogenic gamma function and symbolic 2-plithogenic beta function were presented to pave the way towards achieving the desired goal, which is symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional 2-Plithogenic Calculus.

Keywords: Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Fractional Integration, Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Fractional Derivative, Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Gamma Function and Symbolic 2-Plithogenic Beta Function.

1. Introduction

Fractional calculus owes its origin to a question of whether the meaning of a derivative to an integer order n could be extended to still be valid when n is not an integer. This question was first raised by L'Hopital on September 30th, 1695. On that day, in a letter to Leibniz, he posed a question about $\frac{d^n x}{dx^n}$, Leibniz's notation for the derivative of the linear function $f(x) = x$. L'Hopital curiously asked what the result would be if $n = \frac{1}{2}$. Leibniz responded that it would be "an apparent paradox, from which one day useful consequences will be drawn," [31]

Neutrosophy is a new branch of philosophy concerns with the indeterminacy in all areas of life and science. It has become a useful tool in generalizing many classical systems such as equations [1,9], number theory [2,3], topology [4,5], linear spaces [6,10], modules [4,5], and ring of matrices [7,8].

In the literature, we find many studies about neutrosophic calculus, where some definitions and properties were presented about neutrosophic real functions and numbers [10]. The neutrosophic real functions with one variable were defined only in a special case [11], as follows:

Recently, Abobala and Hatip, have presented the concept of two-dimensional AH-isometry to study the correspondence between neutrosophic plane $R(I) \times R(I)$ and the classical module $R^2 \times R^2$. Also, the one-dimensional AH-isometry between $R(I)$ and $R \times R$. This isometry was useful in defining inner products and norms [10], ordering [9], and neutrosophic geometrical shapes [10].

In [12], the concept of symbolic n -plithogenic algebraic structures was proposed by Smarandache, then it was used on a wide range by many researchers to generalize classical algebraic

structures such as modules [13], spaces [14-15], equations [16], and number theory [17-18]. In [19], the concept of symbolic 2-plithogenic matrices was presented with many applications in the theory of algebraic equations and representing functions. Laterally, symbolic 3-plithogenic matrices and 4-plithogenic matrices were studied from many algebraic sides, especially those which are related to the diagonalization problem [20].

In this work, we use the one-dimensional AH-isometry to turn the general case of symbolic 2-plithogenic neutrosophic real functions with one variable into three classical real functions so we will go from $2 - SP_R$ space into $R \times R \times R$ space. The definitions of symbolic 2-plithogenic integration and symbolic 2-plithogenic differentiation were introduced.

2. Terminologies

We present here some basic definitions and axioms of neutrosophic logic and refined neutrosophic logic.

Definition 2.1. [21]: Let X be a non-empty fixed set. A neutrosophic set A is an object having the form $\{x, (\mu_A(x), \delta_A(x), \gamma_A(x)): x \in X\}$, where $\mu_A(x)$, $\delta_A(x)$ and $\gamma_A(x)$ represent the degree of membership, the degree of indeterminacy, and the degree of non-membership respectively of each element $x \in X$ to the set A .

Definition 2.2.[22]: Let K be a field, the neutrosophic file generated by $\langle K \cup I \rangle$ which is denoted by $K(I) = \langle K \cup I \rangle$.

Definition 2.3. [23]: Classical neutrosophic number has the form $a + bI$ where a, b are real or complex numbers and I is the indeterminacy such that $0 \cdot I = 0$ and $I^2 = I$ which results that $I^n = I$ for all positive integers n .

Definition 2.4. [25]: Let R be a ring, the symbolic 2-plithogenic ring is defined as follows:

$$2 - SPR = \{a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2; a_i \in R, I_1^2 = I_1, I_2^2 = I_2, I_1 \times I_2 = I_{\max(1,2)} = I_2\}.$$

Smarandache has defined algebraic operations on $2 - SP_R$ as follows:

Addition:

$$[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2] + [b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2] = (a_0 + b_0) + (a_1 + b_1)I_1 + (a_2 + b_2)I_2.$$

Multiplication:

$$[a_0 + a_1I_1 + a_2I_2] \cdot [b_0 + b_1I_1 + b_2I_2] = (a_0b_0) + (a_0b_1 + a_1b_0 + a_1b_1)I_1 + (a_0b_2 + a_1b_2 + a_2b_0 + a_2b_1 + a_2b_2)I_2.$$

Definition 2.5. Let $2 - SP_R = \{a + bI_1 + cI_2; a, b, c \in R\}$ where

$$I_1^2 = I_1, I_2^2 = I_2 \text{ and } I_1I_2 = I_2I_1 = I_2$$

Be the symbolic 2-plithogenic field of reals. The symbolic 2-plithogenic isometry (AH-Isometry) is defined as follows:

$$T: 2 - SP_R \rightarrow R \times R \times R; T(a + bI_1 + cI_2) = (a, a + b + c, a + c)$$

Remark 2.6.

1) T is bijective, then it is invertible by:

$$T^{-1}: R \times R \times R \rightarrow 2 - SP_R; T^{-1}(a, b, c) = a + (b - c)I_1 + (c - a)I_2$$

2) T preserves distances, i.e.:

$$\|T(AB)\| = T(\|AB\|)$$

Definition 2.7. Let $f: 2 - SP_R \rightarrow 2 - SP_R; f = f(X(I_1, I_2))$ and $X = x + yI_1 + zI_2 \in 2 - SP_R$ the f is called the symbolic 2-plithogenic real function with the symbolic 2-plithogenic variable, written as follows:

$$f(X(I_1, I_2)) = f(x + yI_1 + zI_2) = f(x) + (f(x + y + z) - f(x + z))I_1 + (f(x + z) - f(x))I_2$$

Definition 2.8. Let $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ a symbolic 2-plithogenic function on $\mathbf{2} - \mathbf{SP}_R$, the we define a derivative of a symbolic 2-plithogenic function $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ as follows:

$$f'_{X(I_1, I_2)}(X(I_1, I_2)) = f'_x(x) + (f'_{x+y}(x + y + z) - f'_{x+z}(x + z))I_1 + (f'_{x+z}(x + z) - f'_x(x))I_2$$

Definition 2.9. Let $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ a symbolic 2-plithogenic function on $\mathbf{2} - \mathbf{SP}_R$, the we define a integration of a symbolic 2-plithogenic function $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ as follows:

$$\int f(X(I_1, I_2)) dX(I_1, I_2) = F(X(I_1, I_2)) = F(x) + [F(x + y + z) - F(x + z)]I_1 + [F(x + z) - F(x)]I_2.$$

Definition 2.10. Let $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ a symbolic 2-plithogenic function on $\mathbf{2} - \mathbf{SP}_R$, we define the definite integration of a symbolic 2-plithogenic function $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \int_{a+bI_1+cI_2}^{d+eI_1+fI_2} f(X(I_1, I_2)) dX(I_1, I_2) \\ &= \int_a^d f(x) dx + \left[\int_{a+b+c}^{d+e+f} f(x + y + z) d(x + y + z) - \int_{a+c}^{d+f} f(x + z) d(x + z) \right] I_1 \\ &+ \left[\int_{a+c}^{d+f} f(x + z) d(x + z) - \int_a^d f(x) dx \right] I_2 \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.11. The most basic interpretation of the symbolic 2-plithogenic Gamma function is simply the generalization of the symbolic 2-plithogenic factorial for all symbolic 2-plithogenic real numbers.

We define a symbolic 2-plithogenic Gamma function as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} \Gamma(Z(I_1, I_2)) &= \Gamma(z_1 + z_2I_1 + z_3I_2) \\ &= \Gamma(z_1) + (\Gamma(z_1 + z_2 + z_3) - \Gamma(z_1 + z_3))I_1 + (\Gamma(z_1 + z_3) - \Gamma(z_1))I_2 \\ &= \int_0^\infty (t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2)^{(z_1+z_2I_1+z_3I_2)-1} e^{-(t_1+t_2I_1+t_3I_2)} d(t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2) \end{aligned}$$

Definition 2.12. Like the symbolic 2-plithogenic Gamma function, the symbolic 2-plithogenic Beta function is defined by a definite symbolic 2-plithogenic integral. Its definition is given by

$$\begin{aligned} B(P(I_1, I_2), Q(I_1, I_2)) &= B(p_1 + p_2I_1 + p_3I_2, q_1 + q_2I_1 + q_3I_2) \\ &= \int_0^1 (t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2)^{(p_1+p_2I_1+p_3I_2)-1} (1 - (t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2))^{(q_1+q_2I_1+q_3I_2)-1} d(t_1 + t_2I_1 + t_3I_2) \end{aligned}$$

The Beta function can also be defined in terms of the Gamma function:

$$B(P(I_1, I_2), Q(I_1, I_2)) = \frac{\Gamma(P(I_1, I_2)) \cdot \Gamma(Q(I_1, I_2))}{\Gamma((P(I_1, I_2)) + (Q(I_1, I_2)))}$$

3. Definition of the Riemann-Liouville Symbolic 2-plithogenic Fractional Integral

We can start by introducing a succinct notation that will be frequently used. From now on, $D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2))$ will denote the symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional integration of a symbolic

2-plithogenicfunction $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ to an arbitrary order $v(I_1, I_2)$ and $v(I_1, I_2)$ is a symbolic 2-plithogenicpositive real number .

Definition 3.1.Let $v(I_1, I_2)$ be a symbolic 2-plithogenicpositive real number. Let $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ be integrable and piecewise continuous on $(0, \infty)$. Then for $(I_1, I_2) > 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$, the Riemann-Liouville symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional integral of $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ of order $v(I_1, I_2)$ is:

$$D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) = \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{X(I_1, I_2)} (X(I_1, I_2) - t(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2)-1} f(t(I_1, I_2)) d(t(I_1, I_2))$$

Remark3.3. :Let $(X(I_1, I_2))$, $X = x + yI_1 + zI_2 \in R(I_1, I_2)$ be a symbolic 2-plithogenicreal function with one symbolic 2-plithogenicvariable, thenwe can write:

$$\begin{aligned} D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) &= D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} (f(x) + [f(x + y + z) - f(x + z)]I_1 + [(f(x + z)) - f(x)]I_2) \\ &= D_x^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(x) + [D_{x+y+z}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(x + y + z) - D_{x+z}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(x + z)] I_1 \\ &\quad + \left[\left(D_{x+z}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(x + z) \right) - D_x^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(x) \right] I_2 \end{aligned}$$

Example3.4. : Let's evaluate $D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} X^{w(I_1, I_2)}(I_1, I_2)$ by definition,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} X^{w(I_1, I_2)}(I_1, I_2) &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{X(I_1, I_2)} (X(I_1, I_2) - t(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2)-1} (t(I_1, I_2))^{w(I_1, I_2)} d(t(I_1, I_2)) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{X(I_1, I_2)} \left(1 - \frac{t(I_1, I_2)}{X(I_1, I_2)} \right)^{v(I_1, I_2)-1} X(I_1, I_2)^{v(I_1, I_2)-1} (t(I_1, I_2))^{w(I_1, I_2)} d(t(I_1, I_2)) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^1 \left(1 - u(I_1, I_2) \right)^{v(I_1, I_2)-1} X(I_1, I_2)^{v(I_1, I_2)-1} (X(I_1, I_2)u(I_1, I_2))^{w(I_1, I_2)} d(u(I_1, I_2)) \end{aligned}$$

Where $\left(u(I_1, I_2) = \frac{t(I_1, I_2)}{X(I_1, I_2)} \right)$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} X(I_1, I_2)^{v(I_1, I_2)+u(I_1, I_2)} \int_0^1 (1 - u(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2)-1} (u(I_1, I_2))^{w(I_1, I_2)} d(u(I_1, I_2)) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} X(I_1, I_2)^{w(I_1, I_2)+v(I_1, I_2)} B(w(I_1, I_2) + 1, v(I_1, I_2)) \\ &= \frac{\Gamma(w(I_1, I_2) + 1)}{\Gamma(w(I_1, I_2) + v(I_1, I_2) + 1)} X(I_1, I_2)^{w(I_1, I_2)+v(I_1, I_2)} \end{aligned}$$

We refer to the above example as the symbolic 2-plithogenicPower Rule. The symbolic 2-plithogenicPower Rule tells us that the symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional integral of a constant of order $v(I_1, I_2)$ is

$$D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} X^{w(I_1, I_2)}(I_1, I_2) = \frac{\Gamma(w(I_1, I_2) + 1)}{\Gamma(w(I_1, I_2) + v(I_1, I_2) + 1)} X(I_1, I_2)^{w(I_1, I_2) + v(I_1, I_2)}$$

And in particular, if $v(I_1, I_2) = \frac{1}{2} + 0I_1 + 0I_2$,

$$\begin{aligned} D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-\frac{1}{2} + 0I_1 + 0I_2} [x + xI_1 + x^2I_2]^0 &= \frac{\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma(\frac{3}{2})} [x + xI_1 + x^2I_2]^{\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{x + xI_1 + x^2I_2} \\ &= \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} (\sqrt{x} + [\sqrt{x + x + x^2} - \sqrt{1 + x^2}] I_1 + [\sqrt{x + x^2} - \sqrt{x}] I_2) \end{aligned}$$

$$D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-\frac{1}{2} + 0I_1 + 0I_2} [x + xI_1 + x^2I_2]^{1 + I_1 + 0I_2} = \frac{\Gamma(2)}{\Gamma(\frac{5}{2})} [x + xI_1 + x^2I_2]^{\frac{3}{2} + I_1 + 0I_2} = \frac{4}{3\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{(x + xI_1 + x^2I_2)^3}$$

$$D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-\frac{1}{2} + 0I_1 + 0I_2} [x + xI_1 + x^2I_2]^2 = \frac{\Gamma(3)}{\Gamma(\frac{7}{2})} [x + xI_1 + x^2I_2]^{\frac{3}{2}} = \frac{16}{15\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{x + xI_1 + x^2I_2}$$

Theorem 3.5. Let $(X(I_1, I_2))$, $X = x + yI_1 + zI_2 \in R(I_1, I_2)$ be a symbolic 2-plithogenicreal function with one symbolic 2-plithogenicvariable. Then for all $v(I_1, I_2), w(I_1, I_2) > 0 + 0I_1 + 0I_2$,

$$D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-w(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) \right] = D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-(v+w)(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) = D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-w(I_1, I_2)} \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) \right]$$

Proof:

By definition of the symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional integral we have

$$\begin{aligned} &D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-w(I_1, I_2)} f(T(I_1, I_2)) \right] \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{T(I_1, I_2)} (T(I_1, I_2) \\ &\quad - X(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2) - 1} \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-w(I_1, I_2)} f(T(I_1, I_2)) \right] d(X(I_1, I_2)) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{T(I_1, I_2)} (T(I_1, I_2) \\ &\quad - X(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2) - 1} \left[\frac{1}{\Gamma(w(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{X(I_1, I_2)} (X(I_1, I_2) \right. \\ &\quad \left. - Y(I_1, I_2))^{w(I_1, I_2) - 1} f(Y(I_1, I_2)) d(Y(I_1, I_2)) \right] d(X(I_1, I_2)) \\ &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2))\Gamma(w(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{T(I_1, I_2)} (T(I_1, I_2) \\ &\quad - X(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2) - 1} d(X(I_1, I_2)) \int_0^{X(I_1, I_2)} (X(I_1, I_2) \\ &\quad - Y(I_1, I_2))^{w(I_1, I_2) - 1} f(Y(I_1, I_2)) d(Y(I_1, I_2)) \end{aligned}$$

$$\begin{aligned}
 &= \frac{1}{\Gamma(v(I_1, I_2) + w(I_1, I_2))} \int_0^{T(I_1, I_2)} (T(I_1, I_2) - Y(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2)+w(I_1, I_2)-1} f(Y(I_1, I_2)) d(Y(I_1, I_2)) \\
 &= B(v(I_1, I_2), w(I_1, I_2)) \int_0^{T(I_1, I_2)} (T(I_1, I_2) - Y(I_1, I_2))^{v(I_1, I_2)+w(I_1, I_2)-1} f(Y(I_1, I_2)) d(Y(I_1, I_2))
 \end{aligned}$$

4. Definition of the RiemannLiouville symbolic 2-plithogenicFractional Derivative

The symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional derivative can be defined using the definition of the symbolic 2-plithogenic fractional integral.

Definition 4.1. Suppose that $v(I_1, I_2) = n(I_1, I_2) - w(I_1, I_2) : n(I_1, I_2) = \llbracket w(I_1, I_2) \rrbracket$ Then, the symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional derivative of $f(X(I_1, I_2))$ of order $w(I_1, I_2)$ is

$$D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{u(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) = D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{n(I_1, I_2)} \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-v(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) \right]$$

Example 4.2. suppose we wish to find the symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional derivative of $X^{m(I_1, I_2)}(I_1, I_2)$ of order $v(I_1, I_2)$ we just need to interchange $w(I_1, I_2) = n(I_1, I_2) - v(I_1, I_2)$, $n(I_1, I_2) = 1$ and

$w(I_1, I_2) = 1 - v(I_1, I_2)$. so,

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{v(I_1, I_2)} f(X(I_1, I_2)) &= D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^1 \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-(1-v(I_1, I_2))} f(X(I_1, I_2)) \right] = D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^1 \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-(1-v(I_1, I_2))} X^{m(I_1, I_2)}(I_1, I_2) \right] \\
 &= D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^1 \left[\frac{\Gamma(m(I_1, I_2) + 1)}{\Gamma((m(I_1, I_2) - v(I_1, I_2) + 1) + 1)} X(I_1, I_2)^{m(I_1, I_2)-v(I_1, I_2)+1} \right] \\
 &= (m(I_1, I_2) - v(I_1, I_2) + 1) \frac{\Gamma(m(I_1, I_2) + 1)}{(m(I_1, I_2) - v(I_1, I_2) + 1)\Gamma((m(I_1, I_2) - v(I_1, I_2) + 1))} X(I_1, I_2)^{m(I_1, I_2)-v(I_1, I_2)} \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(m(I_1, I_2) + 1)}{\Gamma((m(I_1, I_2) - v(I_1, I_2) + 1))} X(I_1, I_2)^{m(I_1, I_2)-v(I_1, I_2)}
 \end{aligned}$$

In particular, we will find the $\left(\frac{1}{2} + 0I_1 + 0I_2\right)^{th}$ order derivative of $f(X(I_1, I_2)) = (X(I_1, I_2))^{u(I_1, I_2)}$:

$$\begin{aligned}
 D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} (X(I_1, I_2))^{u(I_1, I_2)} &= D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{1+0I_1+0I_2} \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} (X(I_1, I_2))^{u(I_1, I_2)} \right] \\
 &= \frac{\Gamma(u(I_1, I_2) + 1)}{\Gamma\left(u(I_1, I_2) - \frac{1}{2} + 1\right)} X(I_1, I_2)^{u(I_1, I_2)-\frac{1}{2}}
 \end{aligned}$$

Example 4.3.

$$1) D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} (x + xI_1 + x^2I_2)^{0+0I_1+0I_2} = D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} \left[D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{-\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} (x + xI_1 + x^2I_2)^{0+0I_1+0I_2} \right] = D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} \left[\frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \sqrt{x + xI_1 + x^2I_2} \right] = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} (\sqrt{x} + [\sqrt{x + x + x^2} - \sqrt{1 + x^2}]I_1 + [\sqrt{x + x^2} - \sqrt{x}]I_2) = \frac{2}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} + \left[\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x+x+x^2}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x+x^2}} + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x+x^2}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x+x^2}} \right] I_1 + \left[\frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} + \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x+x^2}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} - \frac{1}{2\sqrt{x}} \right] I_2 \right) = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \left(\frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} + \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{x+x+x^2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{x+x^2}} \right] I_1 + \left[\frac{1}{\sqrt{x+x^2}} - \frac{1}{\sqrt{x}} \right] I_2 \right)$$

$$2) D_{X(I_1, I_2)}^{\frac{1}{2}+0I_1+0I_2} (x + xI_1 + x^2I_2)^{0+0I_1+0I_2} = \frac{\Gamma(0+0I_1+0I_2+1)}{\Gamma((0+0I_1+0I_2-\frac{1}{2}+1))} (x + xI_1 + x^2I_2)^{0+0I_1+0I_2-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{\Gamma(1)}{\Gamma(\frac{1}{2})} (x + xI_1 + x^2I_2)^{0+0I_1+0I_2-\frac{1}{2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{x+xI_1+x^2I_2}} = \frac{1}{\sqrt{\pi}} \cdot \frac{1}{\sqrt{x} + [\sqrt{x+x+x^2} - \sqrt{x+x^2}]I_1 + [\sqrt{x+x^2} - \sqrt{x}]I_2}$$

Notice that 1) and 2) is equal.

5. Conclusion

Symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional calculus is a more generalized form of calculus. Unlike the symbolic 2-plithogenicinteger order calculus where operations are centered mainly at the symbolic 2-plithogenicintegers, fractional calculus considers every real symbolic 2-plithogenicnumber, $v(I_1, I_2)$. And as it has been briefly noted in this paper , the meaning and applications of this new type of calculus are quite comparable to those of the ordinary calculus, especially when gets closer and closer to a symbolic 2-plithogenicinteger. In the future, studying the symbolic 2-plithogenicfractional differential equations became possible thanks to the definitions mentioned in the paper.

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